

enriched with NaCl (0.7%). The pH was kept at 5.0. The SWC, LRWC, and TI were determined by gravimetric methods and the CSC by refractometry in five replications at 21 d after planting. The SWC, LRWC, and TI significantly diminished under salinity stress in all varieties (see table) because plants could not absorb adequate water. The TI was more pronounced than SWC or LRWC. Plants adjust their

TI as a defense mechanism to compensate for water loss.

Salt-tolerant varieties Pokkali and IR42 had a reduction of 6-7% for SWC, 6-8% for LRWC, and 29-30% for TI, whereas in the salt-sensitive MI 48 and Perla, SWC decreased by 18-20%, LRWC by 16-17%, and TI by 60-67%. Varietal differences in salinity tolerance can be measured using these three plant water parameters.

CSC is another important factor to be considered in plant-water relations. An increase (66-67%) of CSC was observed in all varieties under stress conditions. Increase in CSC is attributed to an extensive accumulation of hydrophilic, osmotically active ions in cells and should not be regarded as a defense mechanism of seedlings under stress conditions. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—Irrigated

Te-Shan-Ai No. 2, a high-yielding rice in China

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Te-Shan-Ai No. 2 (TSA), a high-yielding rice variety with wide adaptability, was developed by researchers at the Rice Research Institute, Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences. It was released for cultivation in China in June 1996.

In the 1990-91 regional tests in southern China, the mean grain yield of TSA was 8.6 t ha⁻¹, 14% more than the local check and 5% more than the hybrid check. In the 1990-93 regional tests in Guangdong and Guizhou provinces, the mean grain yield was 6.9 t ha⁻¹, 14% more than the local check in double-cropped areas; mean grain yield was 8.4 t ha⁻¹, 13% more than the

local check in single-cropped areas (Table 1). TSA was registered in March 1992 and July 1995 by the Guangdong and Guizhou Crop Variety Evaluation committees, respectively.

TSA is derived from the cross Te-qing /Shan-Er-Ai. It successfully combines the high-yield characteristic of the female and the wide adaptability characteristic of the male. In large-scale demonstrations, TSA has not only given high yields but has also shown wide adaptability in both single- and double-cropped areas in southern China. The variety was planted on 685,500 ha in 1991-96 in southern China. In 1994, it became a new check for regional trials. In 1996, it yielded at least 10% more than all other varieties tested (Table 1).

TSA is moderately resistant to blast and resistant to bacterial blight. The average amylose content is 26.4%, and the alkali spreading value is 7.0 (Table 2). One major gene and seven

minor genes located on seven chromosomes seem to control the semi-dwarf character of TSA. The character grain weight plant⁻¹ is related to five quantitative trait loci located on chromosomes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 8. A major gene located on chromosome 4 and a minor gene located on chromosome 2 may control the number of panicles plant⁻¹ (Lin et al 1996). ■

Table 2. Grain quality characteristics of Te-Shan-Ai No. 2.

Grain length (mm)	5.3
Grain width (mm)	2.8
Length-width ratio	1.9
Chalky grain (%)	100.0
Chalky area (%)	12.0
Brown rice (%)	81.3
Milled rice (%)	73.5
Head rice (%)	58.4
Gelatinization temperature (°C) ^a	7.0
Gel consistency (mm)	32.0
Amylose content (%)	26.4
Protein content (%)	9.2

^aIndexed by alkali spreading value: low, 6-7; intermediate, 4-5.

Table 1. Performance of Te-Shan-Ai No. 2 (TSA) in regional tests in China, 1990-96.

Character	South China		Guangdong		Guizhou		South China
	1990 (8 sites, 5 provinces)	1991 (19 sites, 11 provinces)	1990 (17 sites)	1991 (21 sites)	1992 (8 sites)	1993 (8 sites)	1996 (16 sites, 10 provinces)
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	8.8	8.3	6.7	7.2	9.4	7.3	8.4 ^a
Grain yield over check (t ha ⁻¹)	+5.2 ^b	+14.1 ^c	+8.4 ^d	+19.8 ^d	+11.9 ^c	+14.9 ^c	
Growth duration (d)	139.5	138.2	136.0	132.0	155.6	155.3	139.2
Growth duration over check (d)	-1.0	+1.9	+2.0	+3.0	+2.7	+3.5	
Plant height (cm)	104.4	105.6	97.8	99.2	85.7	94.2	104.6
Productive panicles m ⁻² (no.)	351.0	312.0	307.5	388.5	294.0	297.0	282.0
Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	122.8	127.2	109.4	117.7	143.8	126.4	132.6
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	101.9	104.0	93.5	96.2	124.2	99.7	111.6
Seed set (%)	83.0	81.8	85.5	81.7	86.4	78.9	84.2
1000-grain weight (g)	26.6	26.4	26.9	26.6	26.9	26.9	27.2

^aTSA ranked first and outyielded all other varieties significantly at the 1% level. ^bCheck is Shanyou 63. ^cCheck is Gui-Chao No. 2. ^dCheck is Shan-Er-Ai.